

Table for Lay Public Dissemination

Acronym	Autonomous Robot RL
Name of user	MHAMDI faiez
Title	Machine learning by reinforcement for the detection of obstacles in an autonomous driving of Robot (Self Driving).
Objectives (Max 150 words, Calibri 11)	<p>Government data identifies driver behavior or error as a factor in 94 percent of crashes, and self-driving vehicles can help reduce driver error. Higher levels of autonomy have the potential to reduce risky and dangerous driver behaviors. While the Self-Driving considered like a very sensitive field, so a pre-application considered like an important step and here we talk about a virtual environment like a tool that helps to keep dependencies required by different projects separate by creating isolated python virtual environments for them. This is one of the most important tools that most of the Python developers use.</p> <p>We apply a Reinforcement Learning technic by python language using the PyCharm environment for the lane detection.</p>
Impact (Max 150 words, Calibri 11)	<p>While the project that I came with it need more long time given to the training that it be token by the ROBOT, but TERRINet's experience was amazing to give the opportunity for a collaboration within a group that help solve difficult problems. Brainstorming is a good opportunity for the team to exchange ideas and come up with creative ways of doing things. By working together, teams can find the solutions that work best.</p> <p>The meetings that i made with Mr. Alberto and Mr. Fernando, where we plan and we discuss about the solutions and the technics that could be possible to help for a good advancement for the project, help me a lot in my research aspect.</p>